

On the Measurement of Absolute Rates of Migration of Ions by the Method of Moving Boundaries. Part II.

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The 'moving boundary method' can be utilised for the determination of the absolute rate of migration of an ion if the potential gradient under which the boundary moves can be accurately measured. Mukherjee's method (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, **A** 103, 102) of measuring the cataphoretic speeds of colloidal particles is based on this principle. In a previous paper (Mukherjee, Mitra and Bhattacharyya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 177) a method of calculating the absolute rates of migration of both the 'leading' and the 'indicator' ions from known linear displacements of the boundary, moving under directly measured potential gradients, has been developed and applied in investigating rising 'anion boundaries' between hydrochloric and picric acid solutions of approximately 'adjusted' concentrations. The absolute rates of migration of the chloride ion were found to be distinctly lower than the accepted values at corresponding hydrochloric acid concentrations. In view of this and other interesting observations it was considered desirable to work in more detail with the hydrochloric acid—picric acid system.

The difficulties of reproducible measurements with boundaries between solutions of acids are well known (Longworth, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 2741). In view of the high mobility of the hydrogen ion, disturbances arising from heating effects at an 'acid boundary' are particularly troublesome. It was, therefore, considered desirable to compare the results obtained with the system (a) hydrochloric acid—picric acid, (b) sodium chloride—sodium picrate, (c) potassium chloride—potassium picrate. In very dilute solutions of sodium and potassium chlorides, the picrates were not so suitable as 'indicator' solutions owing to the difference in density between the two solutions forming the boundary being negligibly small. The much heavier iodeosin ion was found to be more convenient under such conditions. The iodeosin ion exhibits

a strong red colour even at high dilutions and the boundary could be accurately located with a proper control of the colour of the back ground illumination. The iodeosin ion has been used as an indicator ion by Franklin and Cady (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **26**, 499) and by Longworth (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 1897). Rising boundaries between potassium chloride and potassium salt of iodeosin have been investigated in this work.

The work of previous investigators (MacInnes and Longworth, *Chem. Rev.*, 1932, **11**, 171) shows that the range of concentration adjustment of the 'indicator ion' which according to Kohlrausch (*Ann. physik*, 1897, **62**, 209) should be unlimited for a given concentration of the leading ion, is actually limited depending on the conditions of experiment. Results throwing light on the nature and mechanism of this concentration adjustment have been obtained. Some experimental observations recorded in the previous paper (Mukherjee and co-workers, *loc. cit.*) suggested a possible effect of the potential gradient in the upper liquid on the results though Kohlrausch's theory contemplates no such effect provided that the restoring effect of the current is strong enough to ensure a sharp boundary. Similar observations have been made by MacInnes and Smith (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 2246) and by Cady and Longworth (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 1656) but no explanation of these observations have been given. The effect of the current has been followed in more detail in this work.

The influence of the area of cross-section of the measuring tube on the calculated rates of migration and particularly on the range of concentration adjustment has been studied. Boundaries between mixtures of electrolytes have been investigated. Using a measuring tube constructed from a standard micro-burette, the transference number of the chloride ion has been obtained from the volume swept by the boundary, and the current actually measured simultaneously with measurements of the linear displacement of the boundary. Further, knowing the potential gradients in the different layers, also the absolute rate of migration of the chloride ion has been calculated.

Theory and Method of Calculation.

(a) *Theory.*—The theory underlying the method has been discussed in detail in the previous paper. It will be helpful to reproduce it briefly as follows :

When a potential gradient acts across a boundary between a solution of hydrochloric acid and an equiconducting solution of picric acid such that the faster moving chloride ions are followed by the slower moving picrate ions, an automatic concentration adjustment in the picric acid takes place such that a more dilute solution of concentration c' , governed by the relation $c/T = c'/T'$ comes out, c and c' denoting the concentrations and T and T' , the transference numbers respectively of the chloride and the picrate ions. The concentration c remains unaltered.

Under steady conditions, the potential difference between two fixed planes at right angles to the direction of the current, one in the hydrochloric acid and the other in the picric acid solution, is given by

$$V = i[\sigma_1(x - x_1) + \sigma_2 x_1] \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where i , is the constant current density employed; σ_1 and σ_2 are respectively the specific resistances of layers of hydrochloric and picric acid solutions; x_1 is the distance between the boundary and the fixed plane in picric acid and x is the total distance between the planes.

From equation (i)

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = i(\sigma_2 - \sigma_1) = P \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} &= i(\sigma_2 - \sigma_1) \frac{\partial x}{\partial t} = i(\sigma_2 - \sigma_1) \times \text{the velocity of the boundary} \\ &= Q \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (iii) \end{aligned}$$

P and Q are constants independent respectively of the position of the boundary and time.

Also the potential gradient in the picric acid layer is given as

$$i \sigma_2 = i \sigma_1 + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (iv)$$

It is possible to measure the potential gradients in both layers without measuring the cross-section of the tube if the potential gradient in the hydrochloric acid layer and $\partial v / \partial x$ are directly measured.

The above equations show that in absence of disturbing effects, *e.g.*, those arising from heating and diffusion, (i) the potential difference between the two planes should change linearly with time and also with the distance traversed by the boundary; and (ii) this distance also should be linearly related with time.

(b) *Method of Calculation.* (1) *Rates of migration*—The boundary being located between the side-limbs 2 and 3 (Mukherjee's apparatus *cf.* previous paper) the difference in potential between two silver—silver chloride electrodes dipped into the side-limbs 1 and 2 is measured. Under satisfactory experimental conditions, this potential difference remains constant within $\pm 0.1\%$. Knowing the effective distance between these side-limbs, the potential gradient in the leading solution can be calculated. As the boundary rises, the P D between side-limbs 2 and 3 increases chronologically. The increment corresponding to a given displacement of the boundary is measured, from which the increment per centimetre displacement ($\partial v/\partial x$) can be calculated, on adding this increment to the constant potential gradient obtaining in the leading solution, the gradient in the 'indicator' electrolyte is obtained (*cf.* equation *iv*). By combining these gradients with the distance traversed by the boundary in a given interval of time, the absolute rates of migration of the 'leading' and also of the 'following' ions are obtained.

(2) *Transference numbers.*—The transference number of the 'leading ion' can be calculated with the aid of the equation $T = VcF/it$, where T denotes the transference number and c , the concentration of the 'leading ion'; i , the constant current employed and t , the time during which the volume V has been swept by the boundary. For accurate determinations of the volume, the moving boundary apparatus was constructed from a standard micro-burette. The side limbs 2 and 3 for potentiometric measurements were scaled too wide apart to vitiate the graduations over at least a distance of one centimetre midway between these side-limbs. The boundary was in all cases located in this region and the measurement discontinued when the boundary passed beyond it. The accuracy of the graduations of the tube was tested by a careful recalibration.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Excepting for a few modifications (*vide infra*) the experimental arrangements were similar to those employed in the previous paper

(Mukherjee and co-workers, *loc. cit.*). Rising boundaries between solutions of different concentrations of (1) hydrochloric acid and picric acid, (2) sodium chloride and sodium picrate, (3) potassium chloride and potassium picrate, (4) potassium chloride and potassium salt of iodeosin, (5) hydrochloric acid and mixtures of hydrochloric and picric acids, and (6) potassium chloride and potassium picrate to which varying amounts of potassium chloride had been added, have been investigated.

In the previous work, platinised platinum electrodes had been used for applying the external voltage. The maintenance of a constant current through the cell presented difficulties with these gassing electrodes because of capricious fluctuations of the internal resistance due to irregular gas bubbling at and near the electrodes. The use of platinum electrodes with salt solutions, *e.g.*, sodium chloride and sodium picrate presented further difficulties in that, on the passage of the current, acids and alkalis were formed at the anodes and cathodes respectively. The consequent introduction of the faster moving H^+ and OH^- ions seriously affected the resistances of the original salt solutions and the potential gradient in the upper liquid showed considerable variations (*vide* Table II). The use of non-gassing reversible electrodes, *e.g.*, silver—silver chloride electrodes have eliminated these difficulties.

Measurements have been made with two moving boundary cells—one having a tube diameter of 18 mm., that of the other (the one constructed from a standard micro-burette) being only 6 mm. The effective distance of the first tube was measured as previously described (Mukherjee, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, **A103**, 102) that of the narrow tube was obtained in a slightly different manner; the tube being filled with a solution whose specific conductivity had been previously determined, a current was passed and the potential difference between any two side-limbs, the effective distance between which was required, determined. Knowing the specific conductivity (k) of the solution and the area of cross-section (A) of the tube, the effective distance (l) was calculated from the equation,

$$P. D. = \frac{c l}{k A}.$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

(a) *The $V - x$ and $x - t$ Curves.*—The differential equations deduced in a previous section show that the assumptions underlying the theory being valid (i) the potential difference between

two fixed planes, one in the 'leading' and the other in the 'indicator' solution, should vary linearly with the distance swept by the boundary; (ii) also the linear displacement of the boundary should vary proportionately with time. Experiment shows that the validity of these conclusions depends on the experimental conditions (*vide infra*; also *cf.* Part I, this series).

(b) *Reproducibility of Results.*—The difficulties of reproducible measurements have been discussed in the previous paper (Mukherjee and co-workers, *loc. cit.*). Even with sharp and horizontal boundaries, where disturbances arising from diffusion and undue heating effects were presumably absent, the variations were often as high as 5 % of average values of the absolute rates of migration. Neglecting extreme variations, the observed deviations from average values seldom exceed 2 % in this work. The order of reproducibility is even more satisfactory when the initial indicator concentration is exactly what is required for complete adjustment (*vide infra*).

In calculating the transference numbers in the manner indicated the limitations of the procedure adopted have to be considered. With the more dilute solutions, the total current being comparatively small (of the order of 1 to 2 milliamperes), an error of 5—10 % is involved in measuring the current as the milliammeter used for this purpose reads directly to 1 milliampere only. The magnitude of the current (i') passing through the moving boundary cell has been calculated indirectly from the measured potential gradient (x) in the upper liquid from the equation $i' = XAk$; where A and k are respectively the area of cross-section of the tube, and the measured specific conductivity of the upper liquid which does not change. Table II shows satisfactory agreement between the observed (i) and calculated values (i') when the magnitude of the current is comparatively large; with smaller currents deviations are observed. It will be seen that the transference numbers (TcI') obtained from the calculated values of the current are satisfactorily concordant. Incidentally, the above agreement between the observed and calculated values of the current illustrates the accuracy of the relevant measurements.

(c) *Effect of the Potential Gradient in the Leading Solution.*—In the previous paper (Mukherjee and co-workers, *loc. cit.*) it was suggested that the rates of migration probably depend on the potential gradient in the leading solution though Kohlrausch's theory contemplates no effect of the current provided that restoring effect is strong enough to give a satisfactory boundary. In this work this effect of

the current has been studied in more detail. Table I gives the results of experiments with boundaries between 0.01 *N*-hydrochloric acid and 0.005 *N*-picric acid using different currents and hence different potential gradients in the leading solution,

TABLE I.

Boundary between 0.01N-HCl and 0.005N-HP.

Current in m. amp.	Pot. gr. in HCl (in volts).	$V_{el} \times 10^5$ cm.-sec.-volt-cm.	Max. % variation from average V_{el} .	Current in m. amp.	Pot. gr. in HCl (in volts).	$V_{el} \times 10^5$ cm.-sec.-v ² -cl.	Max. % variation from average V_{el} .
8.5	0.89	81.2		14	1.43	80.7	
						81.1	
"	0.88	81.2		"	1.50	79.4	
						79.3	
"	0.89	80.2		"	1.46	83.7*	
		80.6				78.4*	
		78.0*			Average	80.1	+ .8
"	0.88	80.5				82.1*	- .9
		82.1*					
	Average	80.8	-0.8	16	1.64	79.7	
			+0.5		1.68	81.0	
10	1.05	80.8		"	1.67	82.7	
"	1.01	80.5			Average	80.8	
		80.0					
	Average	80.4	-0.5				
			+0.5				

It will be seen that the variations amongst average rates migration under different potential gradients are of the order of the variations between results of independent measurements with the same potential gradient and are consequently within the limits of experimental error. Below the minimum current employed (ma) a sharp boundary could not be obtained owing to the rest effect at the boundary being too weak to overcome the effects of diffusion and thermal convection, while with a current higher

* Rejected in calculating average values.

The wider tube was used.

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than sixteen milliamperes the boundary became convex upwards giving evidence of undue heating effects. The above observations that the results are independent of the applied potential gradient are in agreement with those of MacInnes and Smith (*loc. cit.*) according to whom the potential gradient has no effect when the solutions are initially adjusted. The hydrochloric and picric acid solutions in the above experiments were approximately of adjusted concentrations.

TABLE II.

Boundary between NaCl and NaP.
(Wider tube used).

Combination.	Current in milliamps.	Pot. gr. in NaP.	$V_p' \times 10^5$ cm-sec-volt-cm.	$N_{el}' \times 10^5$ cm-sec-volt-cm.	Maximum percentage variation from average V_{el}' .		
(1)** 0.02N-NaCl	8.0	3.11	80.25	37.2			
		0.01N-NaP	3.03			80.2	
(2) "	8.05	3.52	81.5	33.7			
			3.39			81.7	35.0
(3) "	8.05	3.48	81.3	33.9			
			3.24			81.3	36.4
			3.48			83.0	34.7
(4) "	7.05	3.29	82.4	31.8			
			3.22			82.9	32.7
			3.13			83.8*	34.0
(5) "	5.53	2.29	82.4	35.8			
			2.36			82.8	34.9
			2.25				37.3
Average			82.1		-0.9 +1.1		
(6) 0.01N-NaCl	3.6	2.76	85.1	38.6			
		0.005N-NaP	2.84			84.9	37.4
			2.94			84.7	36.1
Average			84.9		-2.5 +2.5		

* Rejected in calculating average values.

** The curves have been correspondingly numbered in Fig. 1.

N. B. Expt. (1) was carried out using platinum electrodes; Ag-AgCl electrodes were used in the rest of the experiments.

The need of using reversible electrodes for applying the external voltage for measurements with salt solutions has already been emphasised. Table II gives the results of experiments with sodium chloride and sodium picrate solutions using respectively platinum electrodes and silver—silver chloride electrodes. It will be seen that using the non-reversible electrodes (1) the potential gradients both in the sodium chloride and sodium picrate solutions diminish with time. Using reversible electrodes the potential gradient in sodium chloride remains remarkably constant (the values are not given in the table); the potential gradients in the sodium picrate solutions do not show any regular tendency to diminish. Satisfactory agreement is also to be found amongst the comparatively large number of values of the rate of migration of the chloride ion. Further—while the slopes of the V, x curves using the non-reversible electrodes (*cf.* curve 1, Fig. 1) tend to decrease, the corresponding curves with reversible electrodes are almost straight lines.

FIG. 1.

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FIG. 2.

1 and 2—0.01N-KCl: $N/173\text{-K}_2\text{I}_2$; $c=1.15$ ma. 3—0.01N-KCl: $N/198\text{-K}_2\text{I}_2$; $c=0.725$ ma. 4—0.01N-KCl: $N/198\text{-K}_2\text{I}_2$; $c=0.71$ ma. 5—0.01N-KCl: $N/208\text{-K}_2\text{I}_2$; $c=0.575$ ma. 6—0.01N-KCl: $N/208\text{-K}_2\text{I}_2$.

FIG. 3.

1—0.001N-KCl: $0.0005N\text{-K}_2\text{I}_2$; $c=0.1$ ma. 2—0.001N-KCl: $0.0005N\text{-K}_2\text{I}_2$; $c=0.1$ ma. 3—0.005N-KCl: $0.0025N\text{-K}_2\text{I}_2$; $c=0.47$ ma. 4—0.002N-KCl: $0.001N\text{-K}_2\text{I}_2$; $c=0.2$ ma. 5—0.002N-KCl: $0.001N\text{-K}_2\text{I}_2$; $c=0.2$ ma.

Effect of Tube Area.

The effect of the area of cross-section of the tube on the results has been studied in detail by Cady and Longworth (*loc. cit.*). The numerous experiments of MacInnes and co-workers show that the tube area is an important factor in regulating the range of adjustment of an indicator solution for a leading solution of given concentration. The absolute rates of migration of the chloride ion given in the previous paper (Mukherjee and co-workers, *loc. cit.*) were distinctly lower than the accepted values at corresponding hydrochloric acid concentrations. It was thought that the discrepancy might arise from an injudicious selection of the tube area. With a tube of 11 mm. internal diameter Smith and MacInnes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 1398) experienced serious difficulties arising from 'larger heating effects.' For measurements with acid solutions tubes of very small internal diameters (2 mm.) have been recommended. In view of these observations it was considered desirable to repeat the previous measurements with a much narrower tube (6 mm. bore). Referring to Tables I and IV which record the results of experiments with the wide and narrow tubes respectively, it will be found that using the same moving boundary system (0.01N-HCl and 0.005N-HP) the values of $V_{Cl'}$ with the narrower tube are considerably larger than with the wider tube and are nearer the accepted values.

Boundaries between Acid Solutions and Salt Solutions.

Comparison of absolute rates of migration of an anion (*e.g.*, the chloride ion) from measurements of 'acid boundaries' (*e.g.* between HCl and HP) and boundaries between salt solutions (*e.g.* between NaCl and NaP) is interesting in view of Mukherjee's idea of electrical separation at a sharp boundary. According to Mukherjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 593) the electrical separation which arises from a difference of the transport number of the common ion in the two solutions forming the boundary should be comparatively small at an acid boundary since the mobility of the common hydrogen ion is so great compared with that of either of the unlike ions that its transport number is virtually the same in the two electrolytes.

Referring to Tables III and IV it will be found that using the same measuring tube the values for $V_{Cl'}$ are larger with the NaCl-NaP boundary than with the HCl-HP boundary. This result apparently contradicts a previous observation by Mukherjee (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*)

that the discrepancy between the accepted value of the absolute rate of migration of an ion and that obtained by the boundary method arising from a separation of electricity at the boundary should be less for a boundary between acid than between salt solutions. The contradiction probably arises from an unequal initial adjustment of the indicator solution for a leading solution of the same chloride concentration. Thus comparing the system 0.01N-HCl: 0.005N-HP and 0.01N-NaCl: 0.005N-NaP, it is evident that the ratio $[Cl'] / [P']$ is different for the two systems; in view of the comparatively small percentage dissociation of picric acid though the ratio [total chlorine] / [total picrate] is the same for both.

TABLE III.

Boundary between sodium chloride and sodium picrate.
(Narrow tube).

Combination	Current in milliamps.	TCl'	Max. % variation from average TCl' .	$V_{Cl'} \times 10^5$ cm/sec/volt/cm.	Max. % variation from average $V_{Cl'}$.	$V_{P'} \times 10^5$ cm/sec.
0.05 N-NaCl } 0.025 N-NaP }	4.05	0.597		81.3		
				81.6		
"	4.05	0.593		79.9		
"	4.05	0.587		78.5*		
"	3.95	0.591		79.4		37.1
"	3.95	0.589		80.4		29.8
"				80.0		31.3
"	Average	0.591	-0.7 +0.8	Average	-1.1 +1.6	29.2
"				80.3		29.9
0.02N-NaCl } 0.01N-NaP }	1.7	0.600		84.2		31.5
				85.5		
"	1.1	0.605		84.3		30.9
"	1.2	0.610		85.7		32.4
"	Average	0.605	-0.8 +0.8	Average	-0.9 +0.8	33.0
0.01 N-NaCl } 0.005 N-NaP }	0.95	0.593		88.3		33.2
"	0.95	0.600		86.7		34.9
"				86.8		36.6
"	Average	0.597	-0.8 +0.7	Average	-0.45 +1.2	
"				87.2		

* Rejected in calculating the average values.

TABLE IV.

Boundary between hydrochloric acid and picric acid.
(Narrow tube).

Combination.	Current in milliamps.	$T_{Cl'}$.	$V_{Cl'} \times 10^5$ cm/sec volt/cm.	$V_p' \times 10^5$ cm/sec/ volt/cm.
0.02N-HCl } 0.01N-HP }	5.5	0.172	81.6 80.7	38.5 38.0
..	5.5	0.171	81.2 79.7	35.3 35.3
		Average 0.1715	Average 80.8	
0.01N-HCl } 0.005N-HP }	2.55	0.171	85.6 85.6	35.5
			83.9 Average 85.0	

TABLE V.

Boundary between potassium chloride and potassium picrate.
(Narrow tube).

Combination.	Current in milliamps.	$T_{Cl'}$.	$V_{Cl'} \times 10^5$ cm/sec/ volt/cm.	$V_p' \times 10.$ cm/sec/ volt/cm.
0.05N-KCl } 0.025N-KP }	4.5	0.501	80.3	32.3 32.3
..	4.5	0.504	80.4	30.6 31.2 31.0
		Average 0.503	Average 80.35	
0.02N-KCl } 0.01N-KP }	1.9	0.512	85.2 83.2*	38.9 38.3
..		0.496	86.2 85.1	36.6
		Average 0.504	Average 85.5	

Referring to Tables I and II (results with the wider tube) and also Tables III and IV (results with the narrower tube) it will be found that the values for $V_{Cl'}$ from a particular measurement generally diminish chronologically with the moving boundary system HCl-HP, whereas the effect is less pronounced with the NaCl-NaP system. Also with the HCl-HP system the successive values of the potential gradient in the picric acid layer show a tendency to decrease (*cf.* Part I, this

* Rejected in calculating average values.

series). Since the potential gradient in the picric acid layer is obtained from equation (iv), a gradual diminution of this potential gradient connotes a diminution in $\delta v/\delta x$, the potential gradient in HCl remaining constant. The cause of the diminution in $\delta v/\delta x$ (i.e., the change in P. D. between side-limbs 2 and 3 for a centimetre displacement of the boundary) should be sought in the boundary itself. A mixed layer whose specific resistance σM is less than the original specific resistance σ_2 and whose thickness gradually increases, is perhaps responsible for the progressive diminution in $\delta v/\delta x$. The comparatively stronger heating effects at an acid boundary than at a boundary between salt solutions favours the formation of the mixed layer in the former case.

Automatic Concentration Adjustments at the Boundary.

TABLE VI

*Boundary between 0.01 N-hydrochloric acid and picric acid
(Wide tube).*

Conc. of HP.	Pot. gr. in HP.	$T_{Cl'}$	$V_{Cl'} \times 10^5 \text{ cm./sec./volt/cm.}$	$V_{p'} \times 10^5 \text{ cm./sec./volt/cm.}$
N/200	1.79		80.8 (Table I)	
N/220	1.94	0.184	87.6	34.2
	1.88		86.6	34.9
	1.81		85.5	35.7
"	1.74	0.181	87.0	37.1
	1.86		86.9	34.9
	1.75		86.1	35.7
		Average	86.6	
N/235	1.99	0.188	90.8*	34.9
	1.85		87.6	34.4
	1.81		87.1	34.9
	1.74		84.5	35.2
"	1.83	0.180	88.1	34.4
	1.73		87.3	36.1
N/250	1.67	0.191	96.7	29.2
	1.56		95.9	30.9
	1.50		92.3	30.9
"	1.73	0.189	93.7	27.8
	1.50		93.6	31.9
	1.52		92.9	31.3

* Rejected in calculating average values.

According to the theory of the method as developed by Kohlrausch (*loc. cit.*), the movement of the boundary should be independent of the nature and concentration of the 'indicator' solution, *i.e.*, for a given concentration of the leading solution there should be no limit to the range of concentration adjustment of the indicator solution. The work of previous investigators shows, however, that the range is limited depending upon the relative strengths of the restoring effect and the disturbing influences, *e.g.*, diffusion, convection etc., operating at the boundary. The results of moving boundary experiments have been often found to be misleading due to a failure to secure the necessary condition of adjustment. The low values of $V_{Cl'}$ given in the previous paper (Mukherjee and co-workers, *loc. cit.*) might be referred to this cause. It was, therefore, considered desirable to repeat the previous measurements with varying concentrations of the indicator solution with a leading solution of a given concentration.

TABLE VII.

Boundary between 0.01N-hydrochloric acid and picric acid.
(Narrow tube).

Conc. of HP	Pot.gr. in HP	TCl'	$V_{Cl'} \times 10^5$ cm./ sec./volt/cm.	$V_p \times 10^5$ cm./ sec./volt/cm.
N/100-HCl, N/200-HP	3.84	0.171	85.6 85.6 83.9	35.5
" "	3.80 3.60	0.176	85.5 82.0	37.4 40.4
N/100-HCl, N/220-HP	3.84	0.181	87.7 } 86.8	38.1
" "	3.69	0.181	87.3 } 87.5 Average 87.3 }	39.7
N/100-HCl, N/250-HP	3.47	0.186	90.2 98.5	43.1
" "	3.65	0.186	91.8 90.5	42.1
N/100-HCl, N/277-HP	3.99	0.183	88.8	37.8

Referring to Tables VI and VII it will be seen that the values for $V_{Cl'}$ very largely depend on the initial picric acid concentration. The correct value is obtained within a very limited range of the indicator ion concentration, the range being smaller with the wider than with the narrower tube. The previously observed discrepancy (*cf.* Part I, this series) from the correct value does not arise, therefore, from any inherent defect of the method but is rather to be referred to a failure to secure the necessary condition of adjustment. The curves showing the range of adjustment are given in Figures 4 and 5. As already stated the range (the flat portion of the curve) is smaller with the wider than with the narrower tube. With picric acid concentrations, higher and lower than the adjusted concentration, the values for $V_{Cl'}$ are lower and higher than the correct value. With the wider tube outside the range of adjustment, it is interesting to find that the rates of migration of the picrate ion tend to diminish when the corresponding values for $V_{Cl'}$ tend to increase and *vice versa* (curves 1 and 2, Fig. 4).

FIG. 4.

Curves 1-3 refer to $V_{Cl'}$ (wide tube), $V_{P'}$ (wide tube) and $V_{Cl'}$ (narrow tube) respectively.

FIG. 5.

Curves 1-4 refer to Vcl' (wide tube), Vcl' (narrow tube), ncl' (wide tube) and ncl' (narrow tube) respectively.

FIG. 6.

TABLE VIII.

Boundary between 0.01*N*-potassium chloride and *K*-tetraiodoosin
(potassium salt).

Conc. of KIs.	Current in* milliamps.	Pot. gr. in KIs in volts.	Tcl'. cm./sec./volt/cm.	$V_{cl'} \times 10^5$ cm./sec./volt/cm.	$V_{Is'} \times 10^5$ cm./sec./volt/cm.
† (1) <i>N</i> /173	1.15	3.45	0.453	79.8	49.0
		3.33		75.7	48.2
		3.59		75.0	44.3
(2) ..	1.15	3.61	0.453	79.0	44.9
		3.77		75.5	40.7
(3) <i>N</i> /198	0.725	2.76	0.501	87.3	40.7
		2.76		87.5	40.8
		2.75		87.7	41.1
		2.79		87.9	40.6
(4) ..	0.71	2.49	0.499	88.1	43.6
		2.41		87.5	44.8
		2.53		88.4	43.1
		2.63		87.8	41.2
		Average 87.8		Average 42.0	
(5) <i>N</i> /208	0.575	2.13	0.508	88.1	42.7
		2.00		86.9	44.9
		1.96		86.6	45.7
		1.99		85.5	44.4
(6) <i>N</i> /230	0.675	3.0	0.516	90.4	42.9
		2.51		89.8	
		2.59		87.4	
(7) ..	0.71	2.94	0.524	92.5	42.4
		2.71		92.0	

With 0.01*N*-KCl as the leading solution and tetraiodoosin solutions of varying concentrations as the indicator electrolyte, the range of adjustment (Table VIII and Fig. 6) is appreciably larger and within this range the values for $V_{cl'}$ agree with those obtained from the moving boundary systems NaCl-NaP and KCl-KP and also with the correct value within the limits of experimental error. It is interesting to note that within the range of adjustment the results are very satisfactorily regular and reproducible. Referring, for instance, to Table VIII it will be observed that within this range (i) mutually agreeing values for $V_{cl'}$

* Calculated as indicated.

† The $v-x$ curves have been correspondingly numbered in Fig. 2.

N.B. Narrow tube used in these measurements.

are obtained which also agree with the correct value ; outside this range the agreement is far from satisfactory and the values diminish chronologically ; (ii) the successive potential gradients in the indicator solution do not show any regular tendency to diminish, whereas outside the range of adjustment the values decrease chronologically (*vide* Figs. 2 and 3); (iii) even the values for the rates of migration of the 'indicator ion' which generally show capricious variations are fairly concordant within the range of adjustment. In the light of these observations the condition of adjustment appears to assume a peculiar significance.

To investigate further the effects of automatic concentration adjustments, a boundary between 0.01*N*-sodium chloride and 0.005*N*-sodium picrate solutions was initially formed just below the side-limb 2 and the potential gradient in the upper liquid determined with the boundary

TABLE IX

Boundary between potassium chloride and K—tetraiodosin.

Combination.	Current in milliamps.	Pot. gr. in KI's in volts.	VCl' $\times 10^3$ cm/sec/volt/cm	Max. % variation from average VCl'.	VIs $\times 10^5$ cm/sec/volt/cm.
{ 0.005 <i>N</i> -KCl 0.0025 <i>N</i> -KI's	0.47	2.76	89.5		46.1
			88.6		
" "	0.47	2.84	89.7		45.0
		2.67	90.4		48.3
		2.94	90.3		43.8
		Average	89.1	-0.6 +1.4	
{ 0.002 <i>N</i> -KCl 0.001 <i>N</i> -KI's	0.20	2.80	91.4		47.6
		2.95	91.0		45.1
		2.91			45.0
" "	0.20	2.92	91.4		46.8
		2.89	90.9		47.0
		Average	91.2	-0.3 +0.2	
{ 0.001 <i>N</i> -KCl 0.0005 <i>N</i> -KI's	0.10	3.34	93.1		43.8
		3.11	92.6		46.3
		3.07			
" "	0.10	3.20	92.5		46.1
		3.22	91.8		45.5
		Average	92.5	-0.78 +0.6	

Narrow tube was used

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in this position. The changes in P. D. between side-limbs (1) and (2), and side limbs (1) and (3) due to given linear displacements of the boundary ($\delta v/\delta x$) were recorded. On adding these two sets of values of $\delta v/\delta x$ to the previously determined potential gradient in the upper liquid, two sets of values of the potential gradient in the sodium picrate solution were obtained which being combined with the observed displacements of the boundary gave two sets of values for the rate of migration.

TABLE X.

Time in secs.	Pot. gr. in NaP from changes in P. D. between 1 & 2.	Pot. gr. in NaP from changes in P. D. between 2 & 3.	$Vp' \times 10^5$ cm/sec. from $\delta v/\delta x$ from 1 & 2.	$Vp' \times 10^5$ cm/sec. from $\delta v/\delta x$ from (1) & (3).
259	1.97	1.40	34.2	41.4
544	1.87	1.43	35.1	40.8
795	1.75	1.39	36.9	41.9
1135	1.65	1.37	37.5	41.5

It will be observed that the average potential gradient in the sodium picrate solution is greater in a comparatively thin layer of this solution near the boundary (the $\delta v/\delta x$ values being obtained from potentiometric measurements between side-limbs 1 and 2) than the gradient in a comparatively longer column between the boundary and the lowest side-limb (from potentiometric measurements between side limbs 1 and 3). This indicates that the concentration adjustments (in this case a dilution of the picric acid solution) take place in a layer of the solution behind the boundary and contiguous to it. The picrate ion mobilities calculated from a linear displacement of the picrate ions under larger potential gradients at and near the boundary should be smaller (*vide* Table X) than those calculated with the aid of smaller average gradients in a comparatively long column of the pictrate solution.

The effect of concentration adjustments at and near the boundary is brought out more clearly by the results given in Table XI.

TABLE XI

Combination.	Current observed (i).	Sp. cond. of upper liquid in mhoh (K_1).	Pot. gr. in upper liquid in volts (X).	Current calculated ($i' = XAK$).	Tcl' from i' .	Pot. gr. in the lower liquid (X').	Obs. sp. condy. of the lower liquid in mhoh (K_2).	Calc. sp. condy. of the lower liquid ($K'_2 = i'/AX$).
0'05N-KCl	4'5	0'0077	1'74	4'49	0'502	4'4	0'0028	0'0031
0'025N-KP						4'32		
"	4'5	0'0077	1'75	4'51	0'503	4'61	0'0028	0'0029
						4'51		
						4'49		
0'02N-KCl	1'88	0'0033	1'73	1'89	0'502	3'79	0'0077	0'0014
0'01N-KP						3'76		
"	1'88	0'0033	1'73	1'89	0'492	4'33	0'0077	0'0013
						4'26		
"	1'95	0'0033	1'74	1'90	0'508	4'11	0'0077	0'0013
0'01N-KCl	0'85	0'0017	1'50	0'84	0'502	3'8	0'00059	0'00066
0'005N-KP						3'73		
"	0'85	0'0017	1'50	0'84	0'504	3'75	0'00059	0'00073
0'01N-KCl						3'45		
0'005N-KIs	0'73	0'0017	1'28	0'72	0'501	2'76	0'00058	0'00079
						2'76		
						2'75		
"	0'70	0'0017	1'23	0'69	0'502	2'79	0'00058	0'00084
						2'49		
						2'41		
						2'53		
						2'63		
0'005N-KCl	0'43	0'00086	1'48	0'42	0'501	2'76	0'00030	0'00046
0'0025N-KIs						2'76		
"	0'41	0'00086	1'42	0'40	0'502	2'84	0'00030	0'00043
						2'67		
						2'94		
0'002N-KCl	0'20	0'00035	1'49	0'18	0'502	2'8	0'00012	0'00018
0'001-KIs						2'95		
"	0'20	0'00035	1'49	0'18	0'502	2'91	0'00012	0'00018
						2'92		
						2'89		
0'001N-KCl	0'10	0'00018	1'50	0'093	0'507	3'34	0'000061	0'000083
0'0005N-KIs						3'07		
"	0'10	0'00018	1'50	0'094	0'504	0'2	0'000061	0'000088
						3'22		

In the eighth column of the above table are given the measured initial specific conductances (K_2) of the indicator solutions. Changes in these specific conductances on a current being passed would indicate concentration adjustments. Knowing the potential gradient X' in the indicator solution in the usual manner, the area of cross-section (A) of the tube and the current i , the new specific conductivity K'_2 can be

calculated with the aid of the equation $K'_2 = i/AX'$. This method of determining the changed specific conductivity does away with the need of actual conductivity measurements between small electrodes sealed into the measuring tube (*cf.* Cady and Longworth, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 1656; Hartley and co-workers, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, **30**, 648), a procedure which is not altogether free from objections.

Agreement of Observed Values of $V_{Cl'}$ with Accepted Values.

Onsager's equation for uni-univalent electrolytes takes the form

$$\lambda = \lambda_0 - (0.164 \lambda_0 + 26.81) \sqrt{2c} \text{ at } 35^\circ,$$

evaluating for D , T , λ etc.; where λ and λ_0 are the mobilities at the concentration c and at infinite dilution respectively. If the mobility or the absolute rate of migration of an ion be plotted against $\sqrt{c}$, a straight line should result whose intercept on the axis of rate of migration should give the rate of migration at infinite dilution. In the following table the observed absolute rates of migration of the chloride ion obtained under conditions of adjustment have been summarised.

TABLE XII.

Conc. in g. equiv./litre. (c).	$V_{Cl'} \times 10^5$ cm./sec./volt./cm.	$\sqrt{c}$.
0.05	80.3 (Tables III—V)	0.224
0.02	85.0 (Tables III—V)	0.142
0.01	87.7 (Table VIII)	0.10
0.005	89.1 (Table IX)	0.071
0.002	91.2 (Table IX)	0.045
0.001	92.5 (Table IX)	0.031

The curve (*vide* Fig. 7) obtained by plotting the above values of $V_{Cl'}$ against corresponding values of $\sqrt{c}$ when extrapolated yields a value for $V_{Cl'}$ 93.76×10^{-5} cm./sec. which agrees fairly well with the correct value,

FIG. 7.

TABLE XIII.

Boundary between 0.01-N HCl and mixture of HCl and picric acid.
(Narrow tube).

Current in milliamps.	Pot. gr. in HCl.	Pot. gr. in the mixture.	$V_1 \times 10^5$ cm/sec/volt/cm.	$V_2 \times 10^5$ cm/sec/volt/cm.
6	0.65	0.82	41.8	33.0
14	1.55	1.96	44.77	35.4
		2.00	45.7	35.4
9	0.99	2.00	43.1	33.3
		1.14	41.1	35.5
7.5	0.94		42.6	
11	1.20		38.3	
		1.46	42.7	35.0
		1.47	41.1	33.7
		1.48	43.6	35.5

TABLE XIV.

Boundary between 0.01-N HCl and equiconducting mixture of HCl and picric acid. (Narrow tube).

11.5	1.24	2.0	49.3	30.6
		1.98	50.1	31.6
11.5	1.25	2.04	49.1	30.1
		1.90	50.4	33.2
6.35	0.70	1.14	49.4	30.6
		1.21	40.2	

Moving Boundary Experiments with Mixtures of Electrolytes.

Moving boundary experiments with mixtures of electrolytes are of interest as the results of such experiments are likely to throw light on the conditions obtained at and near the boundary in measuring the

cataphoretic speeds of colloidal particles by the boundary method. A colloidal solution contains electrical carriers of several categories and it thus simulates a mixture of electrolytes.

Moving boundary experiments with mixtures of electrolytes have been carried out by MacInnes, Cowperthwaite and Shedlovsky (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2671) in determining the transference number of the chloride ion in mixtures of sodium and potassium chlorides. Transference number of the hydrogen ion in mixtures of hydrogen and potassium chlorides have been determined by MacInnes and Longworth (*Chem. Rev.*, 1932, **11**, 171).

Table XIII gives the results of experiments with boundaries between a 0.001*N*-hydrochloric acid solution and a mixture of hydrochloric and picric acids having the composition : 100 c.c. of the mixture obtained by mixing 90 c.c. of 0.01*N*-HCl and 10 c.c. of 0.05*N*-picric acid such that the concentration of picric acid in the mixture was approximately the adjusted concentration for 0.01*N*-hydrochloric acid. The boundary in the case of the mixture was not as sharp as with the pure electrolytes owing to the restoring effect being much weaker; a broad band was generally observed. It will be found from Table XIII that on combining the observed speed of the boundary with (i) the potential gradient in the upper liquid and (ii) with that in the mixture, two sets of values are obtained none of which show any agreement with accepted values for the rate of migration of the chloride ion, though an approximate agreement is to be observed with the picrate ion mobility. Table XIV records the results of investigations with a boundary between 0.01*N* hydrochloric acid and an initially equiconducting mixture of hydrochloric and picric acids containing approximately 0.005*N*-picric acid. The values in this case also show closer agreement with the picrate ion mobility than with that of the chloride ion. Finally the effect of addition of varying amounts of the leading solution to the indicator electrolytes has been studied. Table XV shows that in the case of a boundary between 0.02*N*-KCl and 0.01*N*-potassium picrate solutions the addition of increasing quantities of the potassium chloride is marked by a progressive diminution in the values for V_{ci} . Table XVI records similar observations with 0.01*N*-KCl and 0.005*N*-potassium picrate to which increasing quantities of the KCl have been added (*vide* Fig 9). Also the slopes of the corresponding $v-x$ curves (Fig. 8) show a tendency to decrease though the curve (given in dotted lines) for the same combination without addition of KCl to the picrate solution is practically linear.

TABLE XV.

Boundary between 0.02N potassium chloride and 0.01N-potassium picrate to which varying amounts of KCl have been added.

(Narrow tube).

C_{KCl}/C_{KP} in the indicator solution.	Pot. gr. in KCl in volts.	Pot. gr. in the mixture in volts.	$V_{Cl} \times 10^5$ cm/sec/volt/cm.	$V_{P'} \times 10^5$ cm/sec/volt/cm.
2.5%	1.89	4.12	84.3	38.7
		4.25	83.8	37.3
2.5	1.89	4.03	83.4	39.0
		4.03	82.5	38.7
5	1.89	5.05	80.8	30.3
		4.57	79.8	36.2
5	1.92	4.62	81.2	33.8
		4.58	78.6	33.0
			77.0	
10	1.91	3.33	72.1	41.3
		3.13	68.3	41.6
10	1.96	3.73	72.0	37.3
		3.31	70.8	41.4
10	1.74	3.27	69.3	36.7
		3.09	68.9	38.6

TABLE XVI.

Boundary between 0.01N-potassium chloride and 0.005N-potassium picrate to which varying amounts of KCl have been added.

(Narrow tube).

C_{KCl}/C_{KP} in the indicator solution.	Pot. gr. in KCl in volts.	Pot. gr. in the mixture in volts.	$V_{Cl} \times 10^5$ cm/sec/volt/cm.	$V_{P'} \times 10^5$ cm/sec/volt/cm.
2.5%	2.09	4.81	87.4	38.1
			86.6	
2.5	2.08	4.89	87.3	37.3
			88.1	
			87.9	
5	2.02	4.52	85.4	38.2
			83.5	
10	2.04	4.22	79.6	38.6
		4.08	78.2	39.1
10	2.05	4.65	80.0	34.5
		4.55	77.8	35.1
			77.1	

FIG. 8.

- Distance (cm).*
- 1 - 0.02N-KCl ; 0.01N-KP (with 0.001N-KCl) ; $c = 2.3$ ma.
 - 2 - " " : " " (with 0.0025N-KCl) ; $c = 2.15$ ma.
 - 3 - " " : " " (with 0.001N-KCl) ; $c = 2.2$ ma.
 - 4 - " " : " " KCl.
 - 5 - " " : 0.01N-KP (with 0.005N-KCl) ; $c = 2.2$ ma.
 - 6 - " " : " " (with 0.0025N-KCl) ; $c = 2.15$ ma.
 - 7 - " " : " " (with 0.0005N-KCl) ; $c = 2.2$ ma.
 - 8 - " " : " " (with 0.001N-KCl) ; $c = 2.2$ ma.

FIG 9.

The upper and lower curves refer respectively to 0.01N-KCl ; 0.005N-KP (containing KCl) and 0.02N-KCl ; 0.01N-KP (containing KCl).

In the light of the above results, the chronological diminution in the values for V_{01} in independent measurements frequently observed in this and the previous work (Mukherjee and co-workers, *loc. cit.*) is to be referred to a progressive ingress of the upper liquid into the indicator electrolyte. A detailed discussion of these aspects of the problem has to be deferred till further experiments, now in progress, have been completed.

SUMMARY.

1. Rising boundaries between pure solutions of (1) hydrochloric acid and picric acid, (2) potassium chloride and potassium picrate, (3) sodium chloride and sodium picrate, (4) potassium chloride and potassium compound of tetraiodo eosin as also boundaries between suitably chosen mixtures of the above electrolytes have been investigated following Mukherjee's method of measuring the cataphoretic speeds of colloidal particles.

2. The variations of the potential difference between two fixed planes between which the boundary was located with the linear displacement of the boundary have been directly measured and the absolute rates of migration of the 'leading' and 'indicator' ions have been calculated from such variations and the observed rate of motion of the boundary. Simultaneous measurements of the transference numbers of the leading ion have been made from observations of the volume displacement of the boundary.

3. The effects of (a) the area of cross-section of the tube, (b) the strength of the current and (c) the addition of small quantities of the leading solution to an approximately adjusted solution of the indicator electrolyte, have been studied. Experiments throwing light on the mechanism of concentration adjustments at and near the boundary have been carried out. The need of securing the condition of adjustment for obtaining correct and reproducible results has been emphasised. It has been shown that the method gives accurate values of absolute rates of migration of ions and may be applied to ascertain the changes taking place in different layers of the solutions at the boundary. As in the MacInnes method here also the transference numbers can be simultaneously obtained.